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The Mediating Effect of Leadership Trust on the Relationship Between Organizational Commitment and Willingness to Remain in the Profession of Public Elementary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the mediating effect of leadership trust on the link between organizational commitment and willingness to remain in the profession among 300 teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur, the Philippines, using a non-experimental quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Weighted mean, Pearson r , and path analysis using AMOS were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that the level of Organizational Commitment and level of Job Satisfaction are “high,” while the level of willingness to remain in the profession is “very high.” Organizational commitment positively and significantly correlated with willingness to stay in the work ($r=0.162$) and leadership trust ($r=0.573$). Also, Leadership Trust positively and significantly correlated with overall Willingness to Remain in the profession ($r=0.386$). Utilizing path analysis, the study revealed complete mediation of leadership trust on the association between organizational commitment and willingness to remain in work. This means that leadership trust is why organizational commitment can influence the desire to stay in the profession.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher turnover is prevalent worldwide, particularly in public schools (Xu, 2017). Data suggest that over 200,000 educators quit the teaching profession each year for reasons other than retirement, with remuneration, demanding work circumstances, and better career options being the most common (Podolsky, Kini, Bishop & Darling-Hammond, 2016). Meager pay, an uncomfortable working environment, and a lack of professional development programs have been cited for teachers not continuing to work in public schools in the Philippines (International Labor Organization, 2017). These are fundamental problems since continual teacher turnover may result in irregular and lower-quality instruction (Agarwal & Sajid, 2017).

With direct interaction with the students in the classroom, the teacher’s influence on learning is apparent (Emenogu, 2020). Sustaining teachers beyond the first three years is considered critical, particularly in public education settings, since it favors student progress in addition to financial requirements and professional development programs (Casey, 2016). Teachers who stay in their field are satisfied with their jobs, which leads to them discharging their tasks at an ideal level (Eliyana & Ma’arif, 2019). Teachers that remain in the profession exhibit passion for accomplishing their jobs, which increases student motivation and even acts as a foundation for potential educational changes (Han & Yin, 2016).

This circumstance encouraged the researcher to investigate various ways to increase teachers’ desire to stay devoted to their careers. The organizational commitment of the teachers is one element. In essence, organizational

commitment is shown when teachers’ fundamental beliefs, job identity, and professional ambitions fit with the academic institution (Bano, Ishra & Misharat, 2019). When teachers demonstrate organizational commitment, it becomes an extra-role behavior predictor (Bierema, 2016) that results in teachers having a higher favorable view of the organization, resulting in their constant motivation to remain with the organization (Lovakov, 2016). Consequently, teachers are more persistent, creative, and productive (Hanaysha, 2016), which leads to improved professional and job results (Ganta, 2014). This establishes how organizational factors may influence teachers’ desire to stay with their respective organizations. Another important aspect included in this study is leadership trust. Teachers’ confidence in school leaders influences organizational effectiveness (Bakhshi, Kumar & Rani, 2014) since a strong leader-teacher connection leads to excellent work results (Hyman-Shurland, 2016). They are recognized as having the power to influence workers’ motivation and loyalty (Restrepo, 2019). Corollary, the researcher is interested in learning how teachers’ trust in their leaders moderates the influence of organizational commitment on the willingness of elementary teachers to stay in public schools. Also, the result of the study could contribute to the body of knowledge that may be beneficial in the field of education.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of leadership trust on the relationship between organizational commitment and the willingness to remain in the profession of public elementary school teachers in

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the Division of Davao del Sur.

The following objectives were developed in particular:

1. To describe the level of organizational commitment in terms of:
 - 1.1 affective commitment,
 - 1.2 continuance commitment, and
 - 1.3 normative commitment
2. To determine the level of willingness to remain in the profession in terms of:
 - 2.1 intrinsic motivation,
 - 2.2 altruistic motivation,
 - 2.3 perceived professional master, and
 - 2.4 school environment.
3. To measure the level of leadership trust.
4. To ascertain the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1 organizational commitment and willingness to remain in the profession
 - 4.2 organizational commitment and leadership trust; and
 - 4.3 leadership trust and willingness to remain in the profession.
5. To determine the significance of mediation of leadership trust on the relationship between organizational commitment and willingness to remain in the profession of the public elementary school teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To further investigate the depth of this study, the researcher sought various research and publications to refer to several approaches, points of view, theories, findings, and perspectives from different authors on relevant topics and similar research pursuits. In this study, the independent variable is organizational commitment, with indicators based on the analysis of Allen and Mayer (1990): affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. The dependent variable is the willingness to remain in the profession with indicators based on the study of Chiong, Menzies, and Parameshwaran (2017), such as intrinsic motivation, altruistic motivation, perceived professional mastery, and school environment. The mediating variable is leadership trust, based on the study of Tzafrir and Dolan (2004).

Organizational Commitment

Commitment has been defined and quantified several times throughout the last few decades (Gupta, 2017). However, the lack of agreement on its definition does not indicate the absence of a body of knowledge that enables us to separate it from other related conceptions, such as satisfaction, motivation, and implication (Chiang & Liu, 2017). Organizational commitment is a psychological, moral, and logical phenomenon (Jaros, 2017). It considers the many meanings of the connection's genesis and the fundamental variations among the various contributions. Organizational commitment generally pertains to an employee's commitment to remain in an organization. Added by Miller (2003 as cited by Nguyen, Le, Tran, Tran,

Nguyen & Nguyen, 2020), organizational commitment refers to how an individual can remain a member due to a shared interest in and commitment to the organization's goals and values. It is further defined as the mental state of an employee that triggers sustained, long-term commitment to the organization to which they belong (Planer, 2019).

More so, individuals loyal to the firm put in additional time and effort and desire to be a part of the organization, safeguard corporate assets and participate in the company's objectives and values (Wang, Keil, Oh & Shen, 2017). This is important because, in any business, a high degree of organizational commitment typically leads to personnel being more efficient and effective at completing their responsibilities properly (Lencione, 2021), resulting in superior services and outputs (Lizotte, Vedinelli & do Nascimento, 2017). In the context of education, organizational commitment manifests itself in the teachers' psychological connection with the school, allowing them to dedicate their teaching career to assisting in the achievement of the school's defined educational objectives (Amora, 2016). This is critical to recruiting and, more importantly, retaining competent staff, which is relevant to educators in an academic company (Yousef, 2017).

Affective commitment. Commitment to an organization is an organic process that develops because of an individual's attitude toward that organization. One way to describe the progression of the development process is by using the phases and degrees of organizational participation (Triwahyuni & Ekowati, 2017). In an essence, affective commitment is concerned with the way individuals form an emotional connection with the organization because of a favorable workplace environment (Bano, Ishrat & Mishra, 2019). Members who are emotionally invested in the organization stay with the organization because they believe their work arrangement is linked with the aims and values of the organization (Setyowati & Suharnomo, 2017).

Likewise, a person's emotional connection to their employer reflects how they view themselves concerning the company to which they belong and how they find meaning in working toward the accomplishment of organizational objectives (Orlando, Brown, Wilson, Forchheh, Linn & Fako, 2019). Also, to Kermanshahi and Hozhabrnejad (2016), the degree to which an individual's actual experience satisfies their requirements (Lim, Loo & Lee, 2017) and goals of the organization (Grieser, 2021) is a significant factor in determining the intensity of their emotional, organizational involvement.

Because it is both subjective and comprehensive, workplace happiness is a challenging notion to express. This is because everyone has a unique set of requirements and objectives (Nguyen, Le, Tran, Tran, Nguyen, & Nguyen, 2020). Therefore, the level of pleasure individuals feel is determined by several aspects of their life, including their aspirations, education, position in the company, professional objectives, experiences, and day-

to-day activities (Idris & Manganaro, 2017). This mindset is described by Sheldon (1971, as mentioned by García-Juan, Escrig-Tena & Roca-Puig, 2019) as an orientation toward the organization, which ties or attaches the person's identity to the organization. The lack of the factors outlined above can quickly lead to discontent, a prevalent factor leading up to employee turnover (Chordiya, Sabharwal & Goodman, 2017).

In synthesis, commitment to an organization is an organic process that develops because of an individual's attitude toward that organization. Affective commitment concerns how individuals form an emotional connection with the organization. The degree to which an employee's real experience satisfies their requirements and goals about the organization is a significant factor.

Continuance Commitment. Another component of organizational commitment is continuance commitment. This concerns how an employee understands the risks and costs of leaving the company (Lau, 2018). Commerce and Fournier (2001, as cited by Adisa, Mordi & Osabutey, 2017) say that a person's decision to stay with an organization is because of the time and money they have already put into it and the costs of switching jobs (Nikpour, 2017) is an example of continuance commitment. Because of this, people who work hard for their company are less likely to leave (Chiang & Liu, 2017).

Moreover, in this case, to understand this part of the teaching job, you need to look at the pay, benefits, and other salaries related to the social and psychological aspects of the job (Schuckert, Kim, Paek & Lee, 2018). This means that this part shows how the risk of leaving the organization is calculated, especially when the economic benefits they might get from the organization are considered. This makes it more of a contractual attachment (Grego-Planer, 2019). People who work for an organization are more likely to stay with the organization if they have a high commitment to staying in it (Jaros, 2017).

On the contrary, Alsiewi and Agil (2014, as cited by Lau, 2018) mentioned that essential teaching is why some people stay committed. Teachers have a lot of responsibilities and are under a lot of stress. Teaching could be a good choice for people who want a challenging job. Candelario, Tindowen, Mendezabal, and Quilang (2020), posited that accumulated savings and few job options seem to force people to keep doing what they're doing. This suggested that these people are committed because they must be. This means that employees stay with the company because they have other investments they don't want to lose, like pension benefits, seniority, or skills that are useful only to that company. In Idris and Manganaro (2017), people also stay with an organization because they think they don't have any other options and are afraid of losing everything they have put into it.

In synthesis, part of organizational commitment concerns how an employee understands the risks and costs of leaving the company. People who work hard for their company are less likely to leave. Teaching could be a

good choice for people who want a challenging job.

Normative Commitment. The final element of organizational commitment is the normative commitment that focuses on employees' moral obligation towards the organization (Bano, Ishrat & Mishra, 2019). This comprises the way workers demonstrate their loyalty to the company they belong, depending on how they see and accept the reciprocal connection between them and the organization to which they are connected. Wiener and Vardi (1980, as cited by Hardiningsih, Udin, Masdjojo, & Srimindarti, 2020) defined a normative commitment as individual work behavior guided by a sense of responsibility, obligation, and loyalty to the organization. The aspects of organizational commitment that were discussed before, even though they are equally important, operate independently and have the potential to influence personnel on a variety of levels inside a company (De La Salle, 2017). Commitment to one's organization is often seen as essential in determining whether an employee will continue working for an organization and whether they will stay with that company. In synthesis, commitment to an organization arises organically from an individual's mentality.

Affective commitment is how people feel about an organization. This is important for recruiting and retaining qualified workers in an academic organization. Understanding the risks and consequences of quitting the firm is part of organizational commitment. This includes how employees show business loyalty. The average devoted worker believes staying with the company is ethical. Meaningful relationships allow workers to spend more time together, which increases loyalty.

Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Professional development is various approaches. Joyce et al. (1976 as cited by Schechter, 2020) described professional growth as proper and casual arrangements for improving teachers as individuals, people with education and experts, and in terms of their job ability. Professional development improves teachers' ability to perform as competent professionals by teaching them new information, attitudes, and skills. Fullan (1995, as cited by Schechter, 2020) defined professional growth as the sum of formal and informal learning in a complex and dynamic setting. Alaloul, Liew, Zawawi, and Kennedy (2020) have started to use "professional learning" to refer to teachers' continual, concentrated "everyday learning," finding professional development a "limited conceptual word." Day's (1999, as cited in Kulcsar, Dobrea & Gati, 2020) concept emphasizes teachers' continuing professional development in the context of change and its linked parts. Professional development has something to do with the motivation of the teachers to stay or remain in their profession willingly.

Intrinsic motivation. In most contexts, the retention of workers, driven by the employees' desire to remain in their companies, has been and will continue to be a significant problem for organizations across all sectors (Aben,

2020). Organizations search for solutions to this problem by developing strategies to increase job satisfaction (Caldwell, Whewell, Bracey, Heaton, Crawford & Shelley, 2021) and enhance the quality of working surroundings (Flowers & Hughes, 2018). However, in the context of the teaching profession, the fundamental reason teachers remain in it is based on the desire to motivate others and bring about good changes in the lives of their students (Ni & Rorrer, 2018). According to Behrstock-Sherratt (2016), successful teaching emerges from the enthusiasm and love teachers have for their students and the teaching profession.

According to the findings of recent studies (Chiong, Menzies & Parameshwaran, 2017; Harrison, 2017), maintaining high levels of teacher motivation is essential for recruiting and keeping qualified individuals in the teaching profession. The retention of teachers in their chosen profession is often the consequence of job satisfaction for teachers, which comes from enough compensation, meaningful interactions between students and colleagues, administrative support, and a good working environment (Seibel, 2020). In addition, there is a possibility that teachers' motivation to continue in their careers is influenced by the acknowledgment they get from their students' parents and other community members (Fernandes, Peixoto, Gouveia, Silva, & Wosnitza, 2019). In general, it has been shown that factors such as intrinsic motivation, altruistic drive, perceived professional mastery, and the school's atmosphere indicate a teacher's inclination to stay linked with the academe.

Similarly, intrinsic motivation is another indicator in the context of willingness to stay in the profession. It is described as the capacity to undertake an activity or task that intrinsically results in happiness on one's own, regardless of whether one receives any benefits from the outside world (Masdonati, Fournier & Lahrizi, 2017). Genuinely driven teachers exude a feeling of dignity in their work, which is one of the reasons why this kind of motivation is regarded as one of the most critical aspects of teaching. They are shown the highest respect in the way they carry out their work (Shah, Khattak, Zolin & Shah, 2019). They almost always have a favorable attitude regarding their work, which serves as the primary motivation for them to continue in the field.

In synthesis, teaching retention is a significant problem for organizations across all sectors. Successful teaching emerges from the enthusiasm and love teachers have for their students and the profession. Maintaining high levels of teacher motivation is essential for recruiting and retaining qualified teachers.

Altruistic Motivation. The capacity for altruism is the ability to concentrate on the happiness of others even in the absence of concern for one's well. According to Sorokin's (1967 as cited by Han & Yin, 2017) description of altruism, which was used by Putwain and von der Embse (2019), altruism may be broken down into six different sorts of love: biological love, sexual expressions of love; psychological love is love expressed emotionally

in which empathy can be given or received., compassion, generosity, and benevolence; social love is love expressed in positive experiences or interactions; religious love is the perception of God's love; ontological love is the use of love or loving to unite, match, uplift, develop, and authorize; ethical love is the association of love with values such as goodness, honesty, and beauty; According to Veludo-de-Oliveira, Pallister, and Foxall (2015 as cited by Claver, 2020), altruism is a crucial component in both the moral and professional accomplishment of teachers, as well as the development and expansion of inclusive institutions. With altruistic motives, teachers have higher tendencies to stay in the profession and maintain it thinking of the good it brings to the students and the community in general with the purest intentions of service and non-selfish reasons (Plata, 2019). Altruistic motivation establishes a desire among teachers to influence the next generation and become catalysts of positive change in the community (Kiongo, 2020). Anchored on this, altruistic teachers stay in their teaching career as they see opportunities to hone their craft and cultivate their being as they see all these as the highest form of life achievement (Laohasongkram, 2017).

In synthesis, the capacity for altruism is the ability to concentrate on the happiness of others even in the absence of concern for one's well. The concept of altruism describes the standards of social behavior based on the principles of compassion, humility, and humility. One example of selfless conduct is engaging in philanthropic activities.

Perceived Professional Master. Teachers' opinion of their career indicates how successfully they might educate, which is another aspect that contributes to their decision to remain in the teaching field (Cerit, 2019). This relates to how educators evaluate and improve teaching practices and how they align those practices with the learning objectives of their students and the academic community (St-Jean & Duhamel, 2020).

Weiss (1999 as cited in Kulclsar, Dobrean & Gati, 2020).) used data from the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) Schools and Staffing Survey (SASS) for 1987–88 and 1993–94 to look at first- year teachers. She concluded that positive organizational expectations were a reliable indicator of a more substantial commitment to teaching. There was a correlation between little student disciplinary concerns, excellent services, teacher introduction, and professional support, all of which led to high teacher morale and career devotion (Swanson & Mason, 2018). When teachers can see the growth of their students, they often get more invested in the learning process, which results in a better degree of motivation (Paniagua & Sánchez- Martín, 2018). This indicates that the likelihood of teachers continuing to do their duties as educators is increased according to the degree to which individuals view the significance of their jobs as educators. In synthesis, the opinion that teachers have of their career is an indication of how successfully they might educate. This relates to how educators evaluate and

improve teaching practices. When teachers can see the growth of their students, they often get more invested in the learning process.

School Environment. The final indicator of willingness to remain in the profession is the school environment or climate. School environment refers to how the school prioritizes the context of learning, good education and success of students, and sustainability of a holistic learning environment (Harmsen, Helms- Lorenz, Maulana, Van Veen, 2018). According to research, the school environment impacts many different sectors and individuals inside schools. For example, a healthy school atmosphere has reduced children's behavioral and emotional disorders (Ma, Chutiya & Nicoll, 2021). Furthermore, research on school climate in high-risk urban contexts reveals that an optimistic, inclusive, and culturally sensitive school atmosphere may significantly influence urban children's academic achievement (Min, 2019).

A healthy school atmosphere has been found to provide favorable educational and psychological outcomes for students and teachers, while a lousy climate may stifle optimum learning and development (Aben, 2020). Trust, respect, shared responsibility, and concern for the well-being of others may have a significant impact on teachers' and students' interpersonal connections, as well as student's academic accomplishment and overall school growth (Harmsen, Helms-Lorenz, Maulana & Van Veen, 2018).

To summarize or synthesize, teachers need to make a concerted effort to remove all forms of uncertainty from rural classrooms to create an effective school and classroom learning environment. Additionally, they need to ensure that open lines of communication are maintained, enabling them to design an engaging and easily accessible curriculum. Both the students and their families need to be informed of your expectations for their learning, the content being taught, and how they might achieve success in the learning environment to eliminate any element of doubt from the curriculum.

Leadership Trust

At the onset, trust has constantly been considered an essential element in fostering school reforms, especially in leadership in the public school system (Rao & Zaidi, 2020). The openness of teacher and principal connections is encapsulated in teacher professionalism (Nicolaidis, 2019). The transparency of teacher relationships is manifested in collegial leadership. Respect for colleague competence, loyalty to students, independent decisions, and cooperation and support of colleagues characterize professional teacher conduct (Khan, Busari, Abdullah & Mughal, 2018).

Generally, teacher leadership emanates from how the school head or principal monitors students' academic performance, attains and sustains high academic standards, and performs an active, constructive, and supportive connection with the schoolteachers (Mukezakule, 2019).

As Zeffane and Melhem (2017) mentioned, leadership trust could manifest when teachers are confident that the school head or principal will remain true to their expected deliverables and shall investigate the welfare of the teachers, students, and the academic community in general. It is also considered the teachers' general expectancy of the words and actions of their designated school head (Khaola, 2019).

In this way, the leaders complement the educational focus of the school. Educators' emotional and physical well-being is enhanced when they work alongside one another. They put in a lot of effort to discover tools and resources for the classroom as well as people who are ready to share the burden so that they may support teachers in boosting student accomplishment (Banks, Fischer, Gooty & Stock, 2021; Harrison, 2017; Nicolaidis, & Duho, 2019).

In synthesis, trust in school leadership is essential to school improvements. Teacher professionalism opens teacher-principal interactions, principals emphasize student and teacher activity, academic-focused collegial leadership boosts optimism, and collegial leadership affects academic optimism. Teacher leadership helps organize teachers' academic procedures. School leaders who build trust motivate teachers to work more. Teacher leaders may accomplish excellent outcomes by creating, innovating, launching, and sharing initiatives that foster collaborative professional growth and increase student learning. As they improve their leadership, they learn to handle personal, interpersonal, and practical problems. Teachers will learn how to conduct self-directed, teacher-led innovative, and efficient activities. Employees' faith in their bosses and superiors will impact their moral and ethical actions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research tools employed in the study were in the form of a standardized questionnaire adapted from different authors. The questionnaires were modified to fit the research objectives and were further validated by the panel of validators and experts. The expert comments were taken correctly and incorporated in the instrument's finalization, and the overall mean validation of experts is 3.97 and described as very good. The adopted standardized questionnaire is legitimate in its contents since the author has already tested and proven them, and the questionnaire itself was modified to classify the questions. Thus, it has been tested and confirmed. The questionnaire was prepared in a comprehensive form with the assistance of the expert validators to provide the respondents who understood the study's goal and were at ease answering each question, t. For the reliability of the questionnaires, Cronbach-alpha scores were utilized. Also, the questionnaires lifted from the internet had sought permission from the author in the manner that the researcher personally e-mailed them.

Before beginning the first part of the research instrument, the respondents were given explicit instructions about the study's goal and the need for them to provide truthful

responses to the questions that would be asked. In addition to this, they were assured that their responses would not be shared with anyone else since the researcher would be following all appropriate ethical concerns, especially regarding confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity.

The first part of the questionnaire deal with organizational commitment with indicators such as affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment.

The instrument adapted and modified was taken from the study of Allen & Meyer (1997). This part has ten items per indicator. Moreover, the five orderable degrees or Likert scale were employed in evaluating organizational commitment, each with its own set of means and descriptions. The five-point Likert scale was used for the research variables. Following Cronbach's Alpha reliability test results, the questionnaire for organizational commitment has 0.824 effects which suggest an internal consistency of "Good" or low-stakes testing (Streiner, 2003)

As mentioned by Santos, Martins, and Brito (2007),

to complete the Likert Scale, respondents had to choose either a box or a blank in answer to a variety of questions on an object, a stimulus, and an attitude. It was usual practice to immediately use the numbers that were received from rating scales as measures by doing calculations such as computing averages or, more broadly, any arithmetic operations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Organizational Commitment

Organizations are continuously looking for high-performing individuals who can assist them in achieving their objectives, producing specialized products and services, and gaining a competitive edge. This is because organizations need people who can help them achieve their goals. One of the vocations that are held in the highest regard across the globe is teaching. Most students will try to mirror their behavior after their teachers. Teachers are the central figures in every educational system, and many people consider them to be a nation's most valuable resource.

Table 1: Level of Organizational Commitment

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Commitment	0.519	3.53	High
Continuance Commitment	0.440	3.90	High
Normative Commitment	0.345	3.92	High
Overall	0.344	3.78	High

Shown in Table 1 is the level of *Organizational Commitment* of the public elementary school teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur.

It revealed that it was manifested "*Most of the time*" with a mean score of 3.78 (SD=0.344) and described as "High". As shown in the same table, all domains have "high" verbal descriptions such as *normative commitment* (x=3.92, SD=0.345), *continuance commitment* (x=3.90, SD=0.440),

and *affective commitment* (x =3.53, SD=0.519).

Level of Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Shown in Table 2 is the level of Willingness to Remain in the Profession of the public elementary school teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur. It revealed that it was manifested "All the times" with an overall mean score of 4.52 (SD=0.429) and verbally described as "Very High".

Table 2: Level of Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Intrinsic	0.530	4.69	Very High
Altruistic	0.516	4.56	Very High
Perceived Professional Mastery	0.505	4.48	Very High
School Environment	0.509	4.38	Very High
Overall	0.429	4.52	Very High

As shown in the same table, all domains have "Very High" verbal descriptions such as intrinsic motivation (x=4.69, SD=0.530), altruistic motivation (x=4.56, SD=0.516), perceived professional mastery (x=4.48, SD=0.505) and school environment (x =4.38, SD=0.509).

Level of Leadership Trust

Shown in Table 3 is the level of leadership trust of the public elementary school teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur. It revealed that it was manifested "Most of the time" as it has an overall mean score was 3.96 (SD=0.264) with a verbal description of "High". All items under leadership trust have high verbal descriptions.

Significance of the Relationship Between Organizational Commitment and Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Commitment to an organization manifested in a variety of positive outcomes such as employee job satisfaction, motivation, and performance has a decreasing effect on employment turnover hence promoting retention of employees in the organization he/she belongs to. Displayed in Table 4 were the results of the test of the relationship between organizational commitment and willingness to remain in the profession.

Table 3: Level of Leadership Trust

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Believing that managers'/employees' needs and desires are very important to employees/managers.	0.352	4.07	High
Being able to count on my employees/managers to help me if I have difficulties with my job	0.394	4.05	High
Having employees/managers who would not knowingly do anything to hurt the organization.	0.423	3.99	High
My employees/managers are being open and up front with me.	0.423	3.99	High
Thinking that the people in the organization succeed by stepping on other people. (R)	0.837	3.69	High
Employees/managers are always keeping the promises they make.	0.425	3.95	High
Having employees/managers who really are looking out for what is important to the managers/employees.	0.401	3.99	High
Employees/managers are having a lot of knowledge about the work that needs to be done.	0.337	4.04	High
Employees/managers are being known to be successful in the things they attempt to accomplish.	0.315	4.03	High
If I make a mistake, my employees/managers are willing to "forgive and forget."	0.442	3.95	High
Employees'/managers' actions and behaviors are consistent.	0.559	3.88	High
Employees/managers are taking actions that are consistent with their words.	0.378	3.98	High
It is best to share information with my employees/managers.	0.653	3.79	High
Feeling that there is a lot of warmth in the relationships between the managers and workers in this organization.	0.374	4.01	High
Knowing that employees/managers would make personal sacrifices for our group.	0.369	4.00	High
Employees/managers are expressing their true feelings about important issues	0.359	4.01	High
Overall	0.264	3.96	High

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Commitment and Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Organizational Commitment	Willingness to Remain in the Profession				Overall
	Intrinsic	Altruistic	Perceived Professional Mastery	School Environment	
Affective Commitment	-.005 (0.936)	-.047 (0.431)	-.028 (0.637)	.061(0.310)	-.006 (0.923)
Continuance Commitment	.146* (0.015)	.085 (0.157)	.103 (0.086)	.147* (0.014)	.145* (0.015)
Normative Commitment	.259* (0.000)	.242* (0.000)	.250* (0.000)	.279* (0.000)	.309* (0.000)
Overall	.147* (0.014)	.094 (0.118)	.113 (0.059)	.185* (0.002)	.162* (0.007)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Based on the analysis, overall Organizational Commitment positively and significantly correlated with overall Willingness to Remain in the Profession ($r=0.162$, $p<0.05$).

Moreover, the domains of Organizational Commitment also significantly correlated with Willingness to Remain in the Profession: Continuance Commitment ($r=0.145$, $p<0.05$), and Normative Commitment ($r=0.309$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. Consequently, organizational commitment and willingness to remain in the profession have a significant link.

Significance of the Relationship Between Organizational Commitment and Leadership Trust

Any organization's success has been predominantly brought about by how leaders take their part in directing the employees to attain organizational goals and motivate them to develop a sense of commitment to the organization. Displayed in Table 5 were the results of the test of the relationship between organizational commitment and leadership trust.

Based on the analysis, overall Organizational Commitment positively and significantly correlated with overall Leadership Trust ($r=0.573$, $p<0.05$). Moreover, the

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Commitment and Leadership Trust

Organizational Commitment	Leadership Trust Overall
Affective Commitment	.272* (0.000)
Continuance Commitment	.488* (0.000)
Normative Commitment	.685* (0.000)
Overall	.573* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

domains of Organizational Commitment also significantly correlated with Leadership Trust: Affective Commitment ($r=0.272$, $p<0.05$), Continuance Commitment ($r=0.488$, $p<0.05$), and Normative Commitment ($r=0.685$, $p<0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected and contended that organizational commitment and leadership trust have an association.

Teachers who have established trust towards the school head or principal are most likely to develop a positive outlook in the context of their profession even positively affecting their interpersonal relationships which may lead to a desire to remain in their teaching career. Displayed in Table 6 were the results of the test on the relationship between leadership trust and willingness to remain in the profession.

Significance of the Relationship Between Leadership Trust and Willingness to Remain the Profession

Based on the analysis, overall Leadership Trust positively and significantly correlated with overall Willingness to

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Leadership Trust and Willingness to Remain the Profession

Leadership Trust	Willingness to Remain in the Profession				
	Intrinsic	Altruistic	Perceived Professional Mastery	School Environment	Overall
Overall	.266* (0.000)	.259* (0.000)	.358* (0.000)	.408* (0.000)	.386* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Remain in the Profession ($r=0.386$, $p<0.05$). Moreover, the overall leadership trust also significantly correlated with all the domains of Willingness to Remain in the Profession: Intrinsic Motivation ($r=0.266$, $p<0.05$), Altruistic Motivation ($r=0.259$, $p<0.05$), Perceived Professional Mastery ($r=0.358$, $p<0.05$) and School Environment ($r=0.408$, $p<0.05$). As a result, the null hypothesis that there is no meaningful association between leadership trust and willingness to remain in the profession is rejected, and found a substantial link thereto.

effect of leadership trust (LT) on the relationship between organizational commitment (OC), and willingness to remain in the profession (WRP) of public elementary school teachers in the Division of Davao del Sur. Thus, multiple regression extends to path analysis. It facilitates the investigation of more complex models than regression. It can evaluate scenarios with several final dependent variables and “chains” of impact, where variable A affects variable B, which affects variable C (Streiner, 2005). Table 7, on the other hand, illustrates the mediating effect: a path analysis. The data obtained in this table were results after conducting the SPSS AMOS.

Significance of Mediation of Leadership Trust on the Relationship Between Organizational Commitment, and Willingness to Remain in the Profession

Moreover, the model presented in Figure 3, Organizational Commitment and Leadership Trust is the path a coefficient which has an unstandardized regression coefficient of 0.439, standardized regression coefficient of 0.573,

Path analysis was used to demonstrate mediation and enhance the acquired result on the significant mediating

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (Significant Full Mediation)

PATH	ESTIMATES			C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized	SE		
OC--> LT	.439	.573	.038	11.666	***
LT --> WRP	.719	.479	.109	6.508	***
OC --> WRP	-.110	-.088	.084	-1.313	.189

computed standard

regression coefficient of 0.710, the standardized regression coefficient of 0.437, computed standard error of 0.109, and a p-value less than 0.05 which means that the relationship between Leadership Trust and Willingness to Remain in the Profession is significant. The effect size of Leadership Trust on Willingness to Remain in the Profession is 71%. Lastly, the path c coefficient is Organizational Commitment and Willingness to Remain in the Profession has an unstandardized regression coefficient of -0.110, a standardized regression coefficient of - 0.088; the

Figure 1. Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Leadership Trust on the Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Willingness to Remain in the Profession error of 0.038 and a probability value less than 0.05. The effect size or the impact of Organizational Commitment on Leadership Trust is 44% which disavows or rejects completely the null hypothesis.

The path b coefficient is Leadership Trust and Willingness to Remain in the Profession has an unstandardized

Figure 1. Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect

computed standard error is 0.084, and a p-value of .189 which is a greater than the significance alpha level 0.05 which means that it is not significant. The effect size of Organizational Commitment on Willingness to Remain in the Profession is -11%.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings generated in the study, it can be concluded that the public elementary school teachers of Sulop, Davao del Sur in Region XI have a high level of Organizational Commitment, a very high level of willingness to remain in the profession, high level of leadership trust, have a significant relationship between organizational commitment and desire to stay in work, have a meaningful relationship between organizational commitment and leadership trust, and have a substantial connection between leadership trust and willingness to remain the profession. Also, complete mediation was found in this study which means that leadership trust is the very reason organizational commitment can influence the desire to stay in the profession.

More so, this supports Transformational Leadership Theory as developed by Burns (1987), which argues that leaders must establish trust among their subordinates and solidify how they commit to and stay in an organization. Trust in leadership could also foster a shared commitment to organizational goals and an improved leader-employee relationship through coaching, mentoring, and providing both challenge and support. Also, it is up to the organization, business entity, or company to offer motivational schemes for their employees to boost productivity, performance, and leadership trust, not only on the employees' commitment.

Teachers who put students' needs first are meticulous in their planning, allowing them to deliver exceptional lessons and extracurricular opportunities constantly. Problems in the workplace that may be avoided include delay, poor quality, blunders brought on by a lack of attention or judgment, changes in performance, excessive leave, and reasons. Workers also produce more outstanding results when they are open to the thoughts and experiences of their co-workers and actively seek to foster teamwork and

harmony

Teachers that have a strong emotional connection to their institution and are dedicated, devoted, and dedicated to their teaching have a high degree of affective commitment to their education. Teachers who like, feel at ease, and are content with their work are more likely to enjoy, feel at ease, and be satisfied with their work. Teachers may be more successful if their school experiences align with their expectations and if the school can satisfy their fundamental needs, such as the need for friendship, the need to feel comfortable in the work environment, and the need to feel comfortable accomplishing duties. These experiences also have a role in determining the degree to which teachers connect with the school and participate in its activities.

Lastly, teachers who are devoted to their jobs place a persistent emphasis on their students' goals, requirements, and interests. They use a wide array of inventive teaching strategies and methods to cater the training they provide to the specific needs of each student. They try to inspire and include the children while keeping in mind that not all children learn similarly.

REFERENCES

- Adisa, T.A., Mordi, C. & Osabutey, E. L. C. (2017). Exploring the implications of the influence of organizational culture on work life balance practices: Evidence from Nigerian medical doctors. *Personnel Review*, 46(3), 454-473.
- Ahmad, I., Zafar, M. A., & Shahzad, K. (2015). Authentic leadership style and academia's creativity in higher education institutions: intrinsic motivation and mood as mediators. *Transylvanian review of administrative sciences*, 11(46), 5-19.
- Agarwal, P. & Sajid, S. (2017). A study of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intention among public and private sector employees. *Journal of Management Research*, 17(3), 123-136.
- Aggarwal, A., Chand, P. K., Jhamb, D., & Mittal, A. (2020). Leader-member exchange, work engagement, and psychological withdrawal behavior: The mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 423.
- Ahn, J., Lee, S., & Yun, S. (2018). Leaders' core self-evaluation, ethical leadership, and employees' job performance: The moderating role of employees' exchange ideology. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 148(2), 457-470.
- Alghazo, A & Al-Anazi, M. (2016). The Impact of Leadership Style on Employee's Motivation *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 2(5), 37-44.
- Alsiewi AM, Agil SOS, (2014). Factors that influence affective commitment to teaching in Libya. *Journal of Business and Management*, 16(2), 37-46.
- Al-Yaseen, W. S., & Al-Musaileem, M. Y. (2015). Teacher empowerment as an important component of job satisfaction: a comparative study of teachers' perspectives in Al-

- Farwaniya District, Kuwait. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 45(6), 863-885.
- Amora, M. (2016). Teachers' organizational commitment, teaching efficacy belief and level of performance in relation to their pupils' attitudes towards mathematics. https://apiar.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/APCAR_BRR722_EDU-221-228.pdf
- Amstrong, M & Taylor, S. (2014). *Amstrong's Handbook of Human Resources Practice*: Hongkong: Graphicraft Limited.
- Aragon, S. (2016). Teacher shortages: What we know. Teacher shortage series. Education Commission of the States. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED565893.pdf>
- Babalola, M. T., Bligh, M. C., Ogunfowora, B., Guo, L., & Garba, O. A. (2019). The mind is willing, but the situation constrains: Why and when leader conscientiousness relates to ethical leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 155(1), 75–89.
- Babalola, M. T., Greenbaum, R. L., Amarnani, R. K., Shoss, M. K., Deng, Y., Garba, O. A., & Guo, L. (2020). A business frame perspective on why perceptions of top management's bottom-line mentality result in employees' good and bad behaviors. *Personnel Psychology*, 73(1), 19–41.
- Baeten, M., Meeus, W. (2016). Training second-career teachers: A different student profile, a different training approach? Educational Process: *International Journal*, 5 (3), 173-201.
- Bailey, J. (2020). Emphasizing altruism is problematic for physicians. *CMAJ*, 192 (30), E865-E865.
- Balassiano, M., & Salles, D. (2012). Perceptions of equity and justice and their implications on affective organizational commitment: A confirmatory study in a teaching and research institute. *Brazilian Administration Review*, 9, 268-286. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S1807-76922012000300003>
- Bakar, A., Mohamed, S., Suhid. A., & Hamza, R. (2014). So you want to be a teacher: what are your reasons? <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ies.v7n11p155>
- Bakhshi, A., Kumar, K., & Rani, E. (2014). Organizational justice perceptions as predictor of job satisfaction and organization commitment. *International Journal of Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v4n9p145>
- Banks, G. C., Fischer, T., Gooty, J., & Stock, G. (2021). Ethical leadership: Mapping the terrain for concept cleanup and a future research agenda. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 32(2), 101471.
- Bano, K., Ishrat, A., Mishra, KK. (2016). Factors Affecting Organizational Commitment of Teachers In Government And Private Universities. <http://www.ijstr.org/final-print/nov2019/FactorsAffecting-Organizational-Commitment-Of-Teachers-In-Government-And-Private-Universities.pdf>
- Behrstock-Sherratt, E. (2016). Creating coherence in the teacher shortage debate: What policy leaders should, know and do. Education Policy Center at American Institutes for Research. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED582418.pdf>
- Bellé, N. (2014). Leading to make a difference: A field experiment on the performance effects of transformational leadership, perceived social impact, and public service motivation. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 24(1), 109-136.
- Brault, M. C., Janosz, M., & Archambault, I. (2014). Effects of school composition and school climate on teacher expectations of students: A multilevel analysis. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 44, 148-159.
- Brown, S., Gray, D., McHardy, J., & Taylor, K. (2015). Employee trust and workplace performance. *Journal of economic behavior & organization*, 116, 361-378.
- Budihardjo, A. (2013). The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction, Affective Commitment, Organizational Learning Climate and Corporate Performance. <https://cutt.ly/7V0soBY>
- Buragohain, P., & Senapati, N. (2016). Teaching Altruistic Behaviour among Adolescent Students. *SSRG International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(6), 15-20.
- Byun, G., Dai, Y., Lee, S., & Kang, S. (2017). Leader trust, competence, LMX, and member performance: A moderated mediation framework. *Psychological Reports*, 120(6), 1137–1159.
- Caillier, J. G. (2014). Toward a better understanding of the relationship between transformational leadership, public service motivation, mission valence, and employee performance: A preliminary study. *Public personnel management*, 43(2), 218-239.
- Caldwell, H., Whewell, E., Bracey, P., Heaton, R., Crawford, H., & Shelley, C. (2021). Teaching on insecure foundations? Pre-service teachers in England's perceptions of the wider curriculum subjects in primary schools. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 51(2), 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2020.1819202>
- Campbell, C., A. Lieberman, A. Yashkina, with J. Rodway, and S. Alexander. (2017). *The Teacher Learning and Leadership Program: Research Report 2016–17*. Toronto, Canada: Ontario Teachers' Federation.
- Candelario, L., Tindowen, D., Mendezabal, M. J., & Quilang, P. (2020). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction among government employees. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity, and Change*.
- Casey, M. S. (2016). *Motivational factors that sustain experienced teachers in high-need, low-performing public schools: A phenomenological study*. Liberty University. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/75897966.pdf>
- Cerit, Y. (2019). Relationship between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and their willingness to implement curriculum reform. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 22(3), 252–270. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105678791302200304>
- Chen, H. L., & Lin, Y. L. (2018). Goal orientations, leader-leader exchange, trust, and the outcomes of project performance. *International Journal of Project Management*,

- 36(5), 716–729.
- Chiong, C., Menzies, L. & Parameshwaran, M. (2017). Why do long-serving teachers stay in the teaching profession? Analyzing the motivations of teachers with 10 or more years' experience in England
- Church, C.D., He, Z., & Yarbrough, S. (2018). Factors influencing organizational commitment and turnover in nurse residents. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 49(10), 482-488.
- Doan, T.T.T., Nguyen, L.C.T., & Nguyen, T.D.N. (2020). Emotional Intelligence and Project Success: The Roles of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(3), 223-233. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no3.223>
- Eliyana, A. & Ma'arif, S. (2019). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144-150.
- Emenogu, G. N. (2020). School leadership and student engagement in core French.
- Fako TT, Nkhukhu E, Wilson DR, Forcheh N, Linn JG (2018). Factors associated with organizational commitment of academic employees in Botswana. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 10(6), 56-64.
- Fasola, O., Adeyemi, M., & F. Olowe. (2013). Exploring the relationship between transformational, transactional leadership style and organizational commitment among Nigerian banks employees. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(6), 96.
- Fernandes, L., Peixoto, F., Gouveia, M. J., Silva, J. C., & Wosnitza, M. (2019). Fostering teachers' resilience and well-being through professional learning: Effects from a training programme. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 46(4), 681–698. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-019-00344-0>
- Fischer, C., Foster, B., McCoy, A., Lawrenz, F., Dede, C., Eisenkraft, A., ... & Levy, A. J. (2020). Identifying levers related to student performance on high-stakes science exams: Examining school, teaching, teacher, and professional development characteristics. *Teachers College Record*, 122(2), 1-64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146812012200202>
- Flowers, V. Hughes, C. (2016). Why Employees Stay. <https://hbr.org/1973/07/why-employees-stay>
- Ganta, V. C. (2014). Motivation in the workplace to improve the employee performance. *International Journal of Engineering Technology, Management and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 221-230.
- García-Juan, B., Escrig-Tena, A. B., & Roca-Puig, V. (2019). The empowerment–organizational performance link in local governments. *Personnel Review*, 48(1), 118-140. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-09-2017-0273>
- Gaudet, M.-C., & Tremblay, M. (2017). Initiating structure leadership and employee behaviors: The role of perceived organizational support, affective commitment and leader–member exchange. *European Management Journal*, 35(5), 663–675.
- Gelaidan, M. H., & Ahmad, H. (2013). The factors effecting employee commitment to change in public sector: Evidence from Yemen. *International Business Research*, 6, 75-87. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v6n3p75>
- Gonzalez, A. D., Peters, M. L., Orange, A., & Grigsby, B. (2017). The influence of high-stakes testing on teacher self-efficacy and job-related stress. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 47(4), 513–531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2016.1214237>
- Gray, L. & Taie, S. (2015). Public school teacher attrition and mobility in the first five years: Results from the first through fifth waves of the 2007-08 beginning teacher longitudinal study. *National Center for Education Statistics*
- Han, J. & Yin, H. (2016). Teacher motivation: Definition, research development and implications for teachers. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2331186X.2016.1217819>
- Hanaysha, J. (2016). Examining the effects of employee empowerment, teamwork, and employee training on organizational commitment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 229(298- 306), 298-306.
- Hanford, V. & Leithwood, K. (2013). Why Teachers Trust School Leaders. from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1006089>
- Hanifah, H., Susanthi, N. I., & Setiawan, A. (2014). The Effect of Leadership Style on Motivation to Improve the Employee Performance. *Journal Manajemen Transportasi & Logistik*, 1(3), 221-226.
- Hardiningsih, P., Udin, U., Masdjojo, G.N., & Srimindarti, C. (2020). Does Competency, Commitment, and Internal Control Influence Accountability? *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(4), 223 - 233. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no4.223>
- Harrison, C. (2017). Boundary crossing during pre-service teacher training: Empowering or hampering professional growth? *Cultural Studies of Science Education*, 13(4), 1129–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11422-017-9812-6>
- Harms, R. (2016). Experiences of early career teachers and their influences on teacher retention. George Fox University. <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1070&context=edd>
- Harmsen, R., Helms-Lorenz, M. Maulana, R. & Van Veen, K. (2018). The relationship between beginning teachers' stress causes, stress responses, teaching behaviour and attrition. *Teachers and Teaching*, 24 (6). 626-643
- Hassan, S., & Hatmaker, D. M. (2015). Leadership and performance of public employees: Effects of the quality and characteristics of manager-employee relationships. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 25(4), 1127-1155.
- Helms-Lorenz, M., Van de Grift, W., & Maulana, R.

- (2016). Longitudinal effects of induction on teaching skills and attrition rates of beginning teachers. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 27(2), 178-204.
- Henry, J., & Woody, A. (2013). Strategic principal communication. *Journal of School Public Relations*, 34(9), 370-376.
- Herachwati, N. & Rachma, A. (2018). Organizational commitment versus career commitment. <https://knepublishing.com/index.php/KnE-Social/article/view/3388/7136>
- Hersona, S. & Sidharta, I. (2017). Influence of leadership function, motivation, and work discipline on employees' performance. *Journal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 15(3), 528-537. <http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.21776/Ub.Jam.2017.015.03.18>
- Hoy, W. K. & Miskel, D. (2013). Educational Administration, theory, research and practice Ninth Edition New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Hyman-Shurland, Y. (2016). The merits of trust in transformational leadership. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3551&context=dissertations>
- Jadhav, V., Seetharaman, A., & Rai, S. (2017). Employee Expectation to Demonstrate Innovative Work Behaviour in Asia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 4(1), 67-78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2017.vol4.no1.67>
- Jiang, J.Y. & Liu, C.W., (2015). High performance work systems and organizational effectiveness: The mediating role of social capital. *Human Resource Management Review*, 25, 126–137. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2014.09.001>
- Jing, L., & Zhang D. (2014). The mediation of performance in the relationship of organizational commitment to university faculty's effectiveness. *Asia Pacific Education Review* 15(1), 141-153.
- Jyoti, J., & Rani, A. (2017). High performance work system and organisational performance: role of knowledge management. *Personnel Review, Emerald Publishing Limited*, 46, 1770-1795. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-10-2015-0262>
- Jonathan, H., Thibeli, M. & Darroux, C. (2013). Impact investigation of organizational commitment on intention to leave of public secondary school teachers in Tanzania. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234681336.pdf>
- Kahn, D.M. (2015). The value of prior professional skills and experiences: Perceptions of second-career teachers. Oliver Nazarene University. http://digitalcommons.olivet.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1080&context=edd_diss
- Kawamura, Y., & Kusumi, T. (2020). Altruism does not always lead to a good reputation A normative explanation. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 90, 104021.
- Kazin-Boyce, M. (2014). Portraits of novice teacher learning with mentors in urban schools. University of Rhode Island. http://digitalcommons.uri.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1266&context=oa_diss
- Kazlauskaitė, R., Buciuniene, I., Turauskas, L. (2012). Organizational and psychological empowerment in the HRM-performance linkage. *Employee Relations*, 34(2), 138-158.
- Keller, S., & Price, C. (2011). Beyond performance: How great organizations build ultimate competitive advantage. *New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons*.
- Kerzner, M.R. (2020). Why Is Organizational health so important? <https://www.eisneramper.com/organizational-health-0820/>
- Kermanshahi, M., & Hozhabrnejad, N. (2016). The Impact of quality of work life and organizational health on teacher empowerment. *International Journal of Research in Organizational Behavior and Human Resource Management*, 4(3), 44-51.
- Khan, R., Naseem, A., & Masood, S. (2016). Effect of continuance commitment and organizational cynicism on employee satisfaction in engineering organizations. <https://pdf.semanticscholar.org/a915/62fe253576fb40ded30e25cbfad0444988ab.pdf>
- Koster, D. (2017). Motivation in the workplace. <https://content.sciendo.com/view/journals/bsrj/8/2/article-p14.xml?language=en>
- Koul, N. (2016). *Evaluation of organization commitment of teachers: a study in select government colleges of Chandigarh*. <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Vol18-issue12/Version-3/B1812031115.pdf>
- Kumari, N., & Afroz, N. (2013). The impact of affective commitment in employees life satisfaction. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research Interdisciplinary*, 13(7), 25-30.
- Laohasongkram, S. (2017). Saving the world, the right way: altruistic education. https://repository.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1119&context=mapp_capstone
- Lasater, K. (2016). School leader relationships: the need for explicit training on rapport, trust, and communication. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1158155.pdf>
- Latifoglu, A. (2014). Staying or leaving? An analysis of early career paths of beginning teachers in victorian government secondary schools. The University of Melbourne. https://minervaaccess.unimelb.edu.au/bitstream/handle/11343/39774/311431_LATIFOGLU%20file%20properties.pdf?sequence=1
- Lee, S.H. & Jeong, D.Y. (2017). Job insecurity and turnover intention: Organizational commitment as mediator. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 45(4), 529-536.
- Le, B. P., & Tran, Q. T. (2020). Leadership practice for building trust of followers: Decisive factors of organizational performance. *SEISENSE Journal of Management*, 3(2), 45–57.
- Lemoine, G. J., Hartnell, C. A., & Leroy, H. (2019). Taking stock of moral approaches to leadership: An integrative review of ethical, authentic, and servant leadership. *Academy of Management Annals*, 13(1), 148–187.

- Lencione, P. (2021). The health of an organization is the multiplier of its intelligence. <http://www.worksystemscanada.com/work-systems-associates-services/organizational-health/>
- Lim, A., J. Loo, & Lee, P. (2017). The impact of leadership on turnover intention: The mediating role of organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, 1(1), 27-41
- Lizote, S., Vedinelli, M., & do Nascimento, S. (2017). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction: a study with municipal civil servants.
- Lloyd, K. J., Boer, D., & Voelpel, S. C. (2017). From listening to leading: Toward an understanding of supervisor listening within the framework of leader-member exchange theory. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 54(4), 431-451.
- Lögde, A., Rudolfsson, G., Broberg, R. R., Rask-Andersen, A., Wälinder, R., & Arakelian, E. (2018). I am quitting my job. Specialist nurses in perioperative context and their experiences of the process and reasons to quit their job. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 30(4), 313-320.
- Lovakov, A. (2016). Antecedents of organizational commitment among faculty: an exploratory study. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 22(2), 149-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13583883.2016.1177583>
- Lu, W. K. (2018). The effect of employee engagement on continuance and normative commitment to the organization.
- Gagnon, C., John, E., & Theunissen, R. (2017). Organizational health: A fast track to performance improvement. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/people-and-organizational-performance/our-insights/organizational-health-a-fast-track-to-performance-improvement>
- Grieser, R. (2021). The case for organizational health. <https://theordinaryleader.com/blog/the-case-for-organizational-health/>
- Ma, K., Chutiyami, M., & Nicoll, S. (2021). Transitioning into the first year of teaching: Changes and sources of teacher self-efficacy. *The Australian Educational Researcher*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-021-00481-5>
- Marquardt, D. J., Casper, W. J., & Kuenzi, M. (2020). Leader Goal Orientation and Ethical Leadership: A Socio-Cognitive Approach of the Impact of Leader Goal-Oriented Behavior on Employee Unethical Behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1-17.
- Maulana, R., Helms-Lorenz, M., & Van de Grift, W. (2015). A longitudinal study of induction on the acceleration of growth in teaching quality of beginning teachers through the eyes of their students. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 51(3), 225-245.
- Mercurio, Z. A. (2015). Affective commitment as a core essence of organizational commitment: An integrative literature review. *Human Resource Development Review*, 14(4), 389-414.
- Mesdaghinia, S., Rawat, A., & Nadavulakere, S. (2019). Why moral followers quit: Examining the role of leader bottom-line mentality and unethical pro-leader behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 159(2), 491-505.
- Min, M. (2019). School culture, self-efficacy, outcome expectation, and teacher agency toward reform with curricular autonomy in South Korea: A social cognitive approach. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2019.1626218>
- Mo, S., & Shi, J. (2017). Linking ethical leadership to employees' organizational citizenship behavior: Testing the multilevel mediation role of organizational concern. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 141(1), 151-162.
- Mostafa, A. M. S., Farley, S., & Zaharie, M. (2020). Examining the boundaries of ethical leadership: the harmful effect of Co-worker social undermining on disengagement and employee attitudes. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 1-14.
- Nagar, K. (2012). Organizational commitment and job satisfaction among teachers during times of burnout.
- Ni, Y., & Rorrer, A. (2018). Why do teachers choose teaching and remain teaching?
- Nikpour, A., (2017). The impact of organizational culture on organizational performance: The mediating role of employee's organizational commitment. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*, 6, 65-72.
- Nguyen, H. N., Le, Q. H., Tran, Q. B., Tran, T. H. M., Nguyen, T. H. Y., & Nguyen, T. T. Q. (2020). The Impact of Organizational Commitment on Employee Motivation: A Study in Vietnamese Enterprises. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(6), 439-447. <https://doi.org/10.13106/JAFEB.2020.VOL7.NO6.439>
- Northouse, P.G. (2015). *Leadership: Theory and Practice*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Novio, E.B. (2019). Teachers now joining diaspora of Filipinos seeking greener pasture. <https://globalnation.inquirer.net/180294>
- Nurtjahjono, G.E. (2020). The Effect of Job Characteristic, Person-Job Fit, Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance (Study of East Java BPJS Employees). (*JPAS*) *Journal of Public Administration Studies*, 5(1), 5-7.
- Orlando, E., Brown, B., Wilson, D., Forchheh, N., Linn, J., & Fako, T. (2019). *The affective commitment of academics in a university in Botswana*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1212802.pdf>
- Oztekun, O., Isci, S., & Karadag, E. (2015). The Effect of Leadership on Organizational Commitment. *Springer International Publishing, Switzerland*.
- Palta, E. (2019). *Examining the attitudes and the opinions of teachers about altruism*. <http://www.hrpub.org/download/20190130/UJER22-19512565.pdf>
- Paniagua, A., & Sánchez-Martín, A. (2018). Early career teachers: Pioneers triggering innovation or compliant professionals? <https://doi.org/10.1787/4a7043f9-en>
- Paragsa, J. M. (2014). School principals' transformational leadership behaviors and their relationship to

- master teachers' teaching efficacy, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Master's Thesis. Philippine Christian University
- Peng, A. C., & Kim, D. (2020). A meta-analytic test of the differential pathways linking ethical leadership to normative conduct. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 41(4), 348–368.
- Planer, D. (2019). The relationship between organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors in the public and private sectors. [researchgate.net/publication/](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/)
- Podolsky, A., Kini, T., Bishop, J., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2016). *Solving the Teacher Shortage: How to Attract and Retain Excellent Educators*. Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute. https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/sites/default/files/Teacher_Exodus_Infographic.pdf
- Polesel, J., Gillis, S., Suryani, A., Leahy, M., & Koh, S. (2020). The Australian Senior Certificates: After 50 years of reforms. *Australian Educational Researcher*, 48(3), 565–584. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-020-00403-x>
- Pranitasari, D. (2020). The influence of effective leadership and organizational trust to teacher's work motivation and organizational commitment. *Media Ekonomi dan Manajemen*, 35(1), 75-91.
- Putwain, D. W., Remedios, R., & Symes, W. (2015). Experiencing fear appeals as a challenge or a threat influences attainment value and academic self-efficacy. *Learning and Instruction*, 40, 21–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2015.07.007>
- Putwain, D. W., & von der Embse, N. P. (2019). Teacher self-efficacy moderates the relations between imposed pressure from imposed curriculum changes and teacher stress. *Educational Psychology*, 39(1), 51–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2018.1500681>
- Rawung, F.H. (2013). The Effect of Leadership on the Work Motivation of Higher Education Administration Employees. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR- JBM)*, 15(1), 28-33.
- Retrespo, D. (2019). The process of building trust between leader and employee: a grounded theory.
- Ronfeldt, M., Loeb, S., & Wyckoff, J. (2012). *How Teacher Turnover Harms Student Achievement*. <https://caldercenter.org/sites/default/files/Ronfeldt-et-al.pdf>
- Sadia, R., White, B. E., Jantunen, S., Brook, A. H., Koh, K. S. B., Toh, V. K. L., ... & Oram Jr, G. A. (2016). The relationship between employee health, quality culture and organizational effectiveness: Findings from the literature. *Complex Systems: Fundamentals & Applications*, 90, 199.
- Schuckert, M., Kim, T. T., Paek, S., & Lee, G. (2018). Motivate to innovate: How authentic and transformational leaders influence employees' psychological capital and service innovation behavior. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 30(2), 776-796. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2016-0282>
- See, B., & Gorard, E. (2019). Why don't we have enough teachers?: A reconsideration of the available evidence. *Research Papers in Education*, 1-27, 10.1080/02671522.2019.1568535
- Seibel, W. (2020). Autonomy, Integrity, and Values in Public Administration: A Dilemma and a Case. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance*, 3(2), 155-166.
- Setyaningrum, R. P., Setiawan, M., & Irawanto, D. W. (2020). Servant Leadership Characteristics, Organisational Commitment, Followers' Trust, Employees' Performance Outcomes: A Literature Review. *European Research Studies*, 23(4), 902–911.
- Setyowati R, Suharnomo P (2017). Investigating organizational commitment among doctors, hospital nurses and two other professional jobs: A systematic review. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 9(12), 99-106.
- Shah, T. A., Khattak, M. N., Zolin, R., & Shah, S. Z. (2019). Psychological empowerment and employee attitudinal outcomes: The pivotal role of psychological capital. *Management Research Review*, 42(7), 797-817. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-05-2018-0194>
- Sharma, J., & Dhar, R. L. (2016). Factors influencing job performance of nursing staff: mediating role of affective commitment. *Personnel Review*, 45(1), 161-182.
- Silaban, N. & Syah, T.Y.R. (2018). The influence of compensation and organizational commitment on employees' turnover intention. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 20(3), 1-6.
- Solinger, O. N., Jansen, P. G., & Cornelissen, J. P. (2020). The emergence of moral leadership. *Academy of Management Review*, 45(3), 504–527.
- Song, S. & Mustafa, M. (2015). *Factors impacting on teachers' job satisfaction related to science teaching: a mixed methods study*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1074879.pdf>
- Spanouli, A., & Hofmans, J. (2020). A Resource Based Perspective on Organizational Citizenship and Counterproductive Work Behavior: The Role of Vitality and Core, Self Evaluations. *Applied Psychology*.
- Streiner, D. L. (2005). Finding Our Way: An Introduction to Path Analysis. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 50(2), 115–122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/070674370505000207>
- Sutcher, L., Darling-Hammond, L., & Carver-Thomas, D. (2019). Understanding teacher shortages: An analysis of teacher supply and demand in the United States. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27(35), 1-40.
- Suryadi, S.(2018). Teachers' leadership and trust:ots effect on teachers' performance. <http://www.ijsrp.org/researchpaper-0118/ijsrp-p7302.pdf>
- Swanson, P. Mason, S. (2018). The world language teacher shortage: Taking a new direction. *World Languages and Cultures Faculty Publications*. https://scholarworks.gsu.edu/mcl_facpub/62
- Tan, J.P.I. (2015). Examining the socialisation of new teachers through the lenses of positioning theory

- and micropolitical theory. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 24(1), 177-188.
- Tesfaw, T. A. (2014). The relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction: The case of government secondary school teachers in Ethiopia. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(6), 903-918.
- Tezergil, S. A., Köse1, A., & Karabay, M. E. (2014). Investigating the Effect of Trust, Work-Involvement, Motivation and Demographic Variables on Organizational Commitment: Evidence from IT Industry. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(12), 111-122.
- Tiznado, D., Clark, J. M., & McDowd, J. (2020). Cognitive predictors of a performance based measure of instrumental activities of daily living following stroke. *Topics in Stroke Rehabilitation*, 1-9.
- Tran, N. H., Truong, T. D., Dinh, H. V. T., Do, L. H. T., Tran, T. A. T., & Phan, M. H. T. (2020). Significance of teacher professional development in response to the current general education reforms in Vietnam: Perceptions of school principals and teachers. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 78(3), 449- 464.
- Triwahyuni, SR. and Ekowati, V.M. (2017). The Effect of Employee Satisfaction on Employees Performance Through Organizational Commitment. *Management and Economics Journal. (MEC-J)*, 1(1).
- Tümkeya, G. S., & Miller, S. (2020). The perceptions of pre and in-service teachers' self-efficacy regarding inclusive practices: A systematised review. *Elementary Education Online*, 19(2), 1061–1077. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2020.696690>
- Valle, M., Kacmar, K. M., Zivnуска, S., & Harting, T. (2019). Abusive supervision, leader-member exchange, and moral disengagement: A moderated-mediation model of organizational deviance. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 159(3), 299–312.
- Varadharajan, M. (2014). *Understanding the lived experiences of second career*. University of Technology, Sydney. <https://opus.lib.uts.edu.au/bitstream/10453/29255/2/02whole.pdf>
- Veludo-de-Oliveira, T.M., J.G. Pallister, & G.R. Foxall. (2015). Unselfish? Understanding the role of altruism, empathy, and beliefs in volunteering commitment. *Journal of Nonprofit & Public Sector Marketing*, 27(4), 373-396.
- Wachter, J. K., & Yorio, P. L. (2014). A system of safety management practices and worker engagement for reducing and preventing accidents: An empirical and theoretical investigation. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 68, 117- 130. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2013.07.029>
- Wang, L.-Y., Jen-Yi, L., Tan, L.-S., Tan, I., Lim, X.-F., & Wu, B. S. (2016). Unpacking high and low efficacy teachers' task analysis and competence assessment in teaching low-achieving students in secondary schools. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 43(2), 165–183. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-015-0196-x>
- Washington, M.L. (2016). Supporting the professional needs of alternatively certified secondary education teachers. *Walden University*. <http://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=3875&context=dissertations>
- Watters, J.J., & Diezmann, C.M. (2015). Challenges confronting career change beginning teachers: A qualitative study of professional scientists becoming science teachers. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 26, 163-192
- Werang, B.R., Betaubun, M. and Pure, E.A.G. (2015). Factors influencing teachers' organizational commitment (Case study on primary school teachers in remote area of Merauke Regency, Papua, Indonesia), *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 2(10), 122-30.
- Weston, T.A. (2015). Non-Pecuniary factors impacting the retention of new teachers at the secondary level in one Virginia school division. Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University. <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/bitstream/handle/10919/51761>
- Wilkins, C., & Comber, C. (2015). 'Elite' career-changers in the teaching profession. *British Educational Research Journal*, 41(6), 1010-1030.
- Wong, C. P., & Ng, D. (2020). The roles of school leaders in developing future ready learners: the case of Singapore. *International Journal of Educational Management*
- Xu, X. (2017). Stronge & Associates: Why Teachers Leave & the Continual Recruitment Cycle. <https://www.tieonline.com/article/2142/stronge-associates-why-teachers-leave-the-continualrecruitment-cycle>,
- Yildizer, G., & Munusturlar, S. (2021). Differences in perceived physical literacy between teachers delivering physical education in schools: Classroom teachers vs physical education teachers. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2021.1932784>
- Ye, Y. (2016). The effect of working conditions on teacher effectiveness: value-added scores and student perception of teaching. <https://vtechworks.lib.vt.edu/bitstream/handle/10919/71655/>
- Yu, M.-C., Mai, Q., Tsai, S.-B., & Dai, Y. (2018). An empirical study on the organizational trust, employee- organization relationship, and innovative behavior from the integrated perspective of social exchange and organizational sustainability. *Sustainability*, 10(3), 864.
- Zhu, W., Zheng, X., He, H., Wang, G., & Zhang, X. (2019). Ethical leadership with both “moral person” and “moral manager” aspects: Scale development and cross-cultural validation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(2), 547–565.
- Zuljan, M.V., & Pozarnik, B.M. (2014). Induction and early-career support of teachers in Europe. *Journal of Education*, 49(2), 192-205.
- Zoghbi-Manrique-de-Lara, P., & Viera-Armas, M. (2019). Does ethical leadership motivate followers to participate in delivering compassion? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154(1), 195–210.